

Clim4 itis

CLIM4VITIS WORKSHOP MODELLING PESTS AND DISEASES IN VINEYARDS

17-18 FEBRUARY 2020

LIST (BELVAUX, LU)
INSTITUT VITI-VINICOLE (REMICH, LU)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 810176. This document reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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About the project

Climate change impact mitigation for European viticulture: knowledge transfer for an integrated approach (Clim4Vitis) is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, funded by the European Commission under the Twinning instrument of the Horizon 2020 Programme. The prime objective of Clim4Vitis is to strengthen capacity and performance in two main specific fields of research in viticulture & climate:

(1) Grapevine modelling and

(2) Methods and tools for assessing climate change impacts on European viticulture, in general, and on grapevine productivity, quality attributes and risk of diseases and pests in particular.

The consortium comprises the following partners: Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD) – coordinator; Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK); Università degli studi di Firenze (UNIFI); Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST); and Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI).

For further project related information, please visit the Clim4Vitis project website - <https://clim4vitis.eu/>

About the event

This is the third workshop being organised within the framework of the Clim4Vitis project. The focus will be on pest and disease related risks in changing climate. Day 1 of the workshop will be dedicated to prediction and modelling of population dynamics of viticultural pests. On the second day, epidemiologic models for viticultural diseases will be presented.

Furthermore, viticulture decision support tools/platforms and their application will be discussed in detail. After each presentation, the audience will be engaged on the topics presented. A final round table will address the main findings discussed during the workshop.

Prominent invited speakers from different European countries will provide state-of-the-art information on pertinent topics, particularly under the current context of changing climates.

The Clim4Vitis project team expresses sincere gratitude to all the participants.

Agenda

Dissemination Flyer

Clim4Vitis
Climate change impact mitigation
for European viticulture

CLIM4VITIS WORKSHOP

17-18 February 2020
LIST, Luxembourg

CLIM4VITIS INTRODUCTION

Clim4Vitis is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project, funded by the European Commission under the Twinning instrument of the Horizon 2020 Programme. The project aims to promote knowledge transfer and science and technology (S&T) capacity building in viticulture and climate change. Clim4Vitis will devise new methods and tools for modelling grapevines, and for assessing climate change impacts on European viticulture.

CLIM4VITIS WORKSHOP

This workshop will focus on pest and disease related risks in changing climate. Day one of the workshop will be dedicated to prediction and modelling of population dynamics of viticultural pests. On the second day epidemiologic models for viticultural diseases will be presented. Furthermore, viticulture decision support tools/platforms and their application will be discussed in detail. After each presentation, the audience will be engaged on the topics presented. A final round table will address the main findings discussed during the workshop.

Target audience: Researchers from partner institutions, agronomist and stakeholders from the winemaking sector, MSc and PhD students.

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www.clim4vitis.eu
www.researchgate.net/project/Clim4Vitis-H2020-Twinning
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utad **CITAB** **PIK** **UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI FIRENZE** **LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY** **LIST** **spi**
Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação

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AGENDA

17 FEB

41, rue Brill, L-4422
 LIST, Belvaux

13:00 – 13:30

Welcome and Registration

13:30 – 13:45

Introduction

Joao Santos – UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal | Lucien Hoffmann – LIST, Luxembourg

13:45 – 14:15

Analyzing pest and disease related risks in a changing climate

Sebastien Zito – University of Burgundy, Dijon, France

14:15 – 14:45

Modelling disease dissemination as a tool for Flavescence dorée containment

Michael Maixner – Julius-Kühn-Institute, Siebeldingen, Germany

14:45 – 15:15

Coffee Break

15:15 – 15:45

SIMKEF: A decision support system to predict *Drosophila suzukii* population dynamics

Alicia Winkler – ZEPP, Bad Kreuznach, Germany

15:45 – 16:15

Predicting field population dynamics of anholocyclic hibernating grape phylloxera in commercial vineyards under climate change conditions

Astrid Froneck – BOKU, Tulln, Austria

16:15 – 16:45

Which changes we have to expect in the dynamic of *Lobesia botrana* for Germany until 2060 AD?

Thomas Kartschall, PIK, Potsdam, Germany

16:45 – 17:30

Round-table discussion

18 FEB

8, rue Nic Kieffer L-5551
 Institut Viti-vinicole (IVV), Remich

09:00 – 09:15

Introduction

Dr. Roby Ley & Serge Fischer – IVV, Remich, Luxembourg

09:15 – 09:45

Epidemiological models for vineyard diseases. Why we should trust in them?

Elisa Gonzalez-Dominguez - Horta srl, Piacenza, Italy

09:45 – 10:15

The viticultural decision support platforms Agrometeo and VitiMeteo

Pierre-Henri Dubuis - Agroscope, CH-Changins, Nyon, Switzerland

10:15 – 10:45

Coffee Break

10:45 – 11:15

Downy mildew forecast model and its successful application in practise (Rheingau, Germany)

Beate Berkelmann-Lohnertz - Hochschule Geisenheim University, Geisenheim, Germany

11:15 – 11:45

Application of the decision support tools of the VitiMeteo platform in practical viticulture

Gottfried Bleyer - Staatliches Weinbauinstitut, Freiburg, Germany

11:45 – 12:15

From modelling to decision support and back – Lessons Learned in 20 Years

Roland Krause - Geosens, Schallstadt, Germany

12:15 – 13:00

Round-table discussion

List of presentations

Day 1

Monday, 17 February

41, rue Brill, L-4422

LIST, Belvaux

13:00 – 13:30: Welcome and Registration

13:30 – 13:45: Introduction

Thomas Kallstenius, Lucien Hoffmann & Joao Santos, LIST & UTAD

13:45 – 14:15: Analyzing pest and disease related risks in changing climate

Sebastien Zito, Université de Bourgogne, F-Dijon

14:15 – 14:45: Modeling disease dissemination as a tool for Flavescence dorée containment

Michael Maixner, Julius-Kühn-Institut, D-Sieboldingen

14:45 – 15:15: Coffee-Break

15:15 – 15:45: SIMKEF: A decision support system to predict *Drosophila suzukii* population dynamics

Alicia Winkler, ZEPP, D-Bad Kreuznach

15:45 – 16:15: Predicting field population dynamics of anholocyclic hibernating grape phylloxera (*Daktulosphaira vitifoliae* Fitch) in commercial vineyards under climate change conditions: Pilot Study Year 2019: Validating a collecting strategy for individual fields

Astrid Froneck, Boku, A-Tulln

16:15 – 16:45 Which changes we have to expect in the dynamic of *Lobesia botrana* for Germany until 2060 AD?

Thomas Kartschall, PIK, D-Potsdam

16:45 – 17:30: Round-table discussion

Day 2

Tuesday, 18 February

8, rue Nic Kieffer L-5551

Institut Viti-vinicole (IVV), Remich

09:00 – 09:15: Introduction

Dr. Roby Ley & Serge Fischer, Institut Viti-vinicole

09:15 – 09:45: Epidemiological models for vineyard diseases. Why we should trust in them?

Elisa Gonzalez-Dominguez, Horta srl., I-Piacenza

09:45 – 10:15: The viticultural decision support platforms Agrometeo and VitiMeteo

Pierre-Henri Dubuis, Agroscope, CH-Changins

10:15-10:45: Coffee-Break

10:45 – 11:15: Downy mildew forecast model and its successful application in practise (Rheingau, Germany)

Beate Berkelmann-Löhnertz, Hochschule Geisenheim University, D-Geisenheim

11:15 – 11:45: Application of the decision support tools of the VitiMeteo platform in practical viticulture

Gottfried Bleyer, WBI, D-Freiburg

11:45 – 12:15: From modelling to decision support and back – lessons learned in 20 years

Roland Krause, Geosens, D-Schallstadt

12:15 – 13:00: Round-table discussion

Abstracts

Day 1

Monday, 17 February
41, rue Brill, L-4422
LIST, Belvaux

Analysing pest and disease related risks in a changing climate

Zito¹ S., Bois^{1,2} B., Castel¹ T., Richard¹ Y., Rega¹ M., Pergaud¹ J., Weens¹ V., Meylon¹ R., Ortega¹ C., Caffara³ A., Garin³ G.

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ABSTRACT

To study the possible projected climate change impacts on pest and diseases in viticulture, daily climate data are required. The coarse resolution of General Circulation Models (GCM; with a resolution from 125 to 300 km per “pixel”) don't provide relevant data to match the extent of the regional vineyards area. Better spatial resolution for climate data are needed toward impact assessment and analysis. Such refinement of spatial resolution is called “downscaling”. Here the approach is to use a statistical downscaling method based on the empirical links between large-scale (GCM outputs) and local-scale (Météo-France analysis data). Due to low needs for computation compare to dynamical downscaling such an approach permits to account for climate change uncertainties. Downscaled climate data are used to feed crop and diseases/pest models to simulate the evolution of phytosanitary risk in the middle. We illustrate here the whole process with the case study of powdery mildew in wine-producing regions of Northeast France. Climate data of 19 GCM have been, with the quantile mapping method, downscaled and debiased to a 8 km target resolution. Two approaches were tested to address the potential evolution of the disease risk with climate change. An empirical method based on multilinear regression between monthly climate indices and the proportion of vineyards with diseases symptoms and, a mechanistic approach, with an infection model of *E. necator* using daily climate inputs and calibrate with diseases symptoms observations.

Modeling disease dissemination as a tool for Flavescence dorée containment

Maixner M.

Julius Kühn-Institut (JKI), Institute for Plant Protection in Fruit Crops and Viticulture, Siebeldingen,
Germany

ABSTRACT

Flavescence dorée (FD) is a quarantine disease of grapevine with great economic importance. It is widespread in southern Europe and steadily extending its range to central European regions. Phytoplasmas of phylogenetic subgroup 16SrV-C and -D are associated with FD and transmitted by the introduced Nearctic leafhopper *Scaphoideus titanus* (Cicadellidae: Deltocephalinae), a strictly ampelophagous vector. The only means of control of FD - uprooting of infected vines and insecticide control of the vector - are mandatory in affected areas, but have negative implications on integrated viticulture. The prevention of further dissemination of FD is therefore of outstanding importance. *S. titanus* plays a key role for FD outbreaks, since it is the only natural vector transmitting FD phytoplasmas (FDp) from vine to vine which enables disease outbreaks from single infected vines. Nevertheless, FD associated phytoplasmas are also present in the wild compartment, with alder (*Alnus glutinosa*) and *Clematis vitalba* as principal alternative host plants. A recent analysis of the complex epidemiology of FDp revealed the presence of >100 different isolates of subgroup 16SrV-C in alder trees, however, only few of those isolates are known from FD outbreaks (Malembic-Maher et al., 2019). Deltocephalinae living on alder have been identified as competent vectors of some of those isolates, but their vectoring ability to grapevine requires verification. FDp isolates from *C. vitalba* are transmitted to grapevine by the planthopper *Dictyophara europaea*.

There are three means of dissemination of the disease: (i) infected propagation material, (ii) local spread by *S. titanus*, or (iii) transmission from alternative host plants to grapevine by Deltocephalinae leafhoppers. In any case, further disease spread depends on the presence of *S. titanus*. An analysis of previous FD outbreaks revealed that 94 % were caused by (i) and (ii) while only 6 % could be attributed to an emergence from wild reservoirs (EFSA-PLH, 2016). Models for FD spread to further EU NUTS-2 regions were established based on historic outbreaks in order to predict the efficiency of different management and containment regimes in Europe (EFSA-PLH, 2016).

Modeling FD-epidemics is important for the setup of effective management strategies in affected regions as well as the assessment of the risk of FD-outbreaks in disease free areas. Detailed knowledge of the complex epidemiology of FD on a regional scale is essential for reliable modeling. Kopacka et al. (2017) modeled the spread of FD in two areas of southern Austria with different environmental and viticultural conditions and derived recommendations for an optimal management of FD.

In yet disease free areas like Germany, monitoring for both FD infected vines and the vector *S. titanus* is crucial for early detection and containment of initial infestations. We are therefore collecting information about the prevalence FD related isolates in the wild compartment and the biology, infestation and vectoring efficiency of alternative vectors in order to assess the risk of FD emergence from wild reservoirs. Monitoring strategies are developed based on field observations of the relationship between the occurrence of FD-related infections in grapevine and landscape structures favoring the presence of wild reservoir plants. The analysis of possible dispersal routes after introduction will become particularly important in the light of the further range expansion of *S. titanus*. It will be the prerequisite for rational containment and control

strategies, but requires further epidemiological studies to identify the main drivers of disease spread.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded in part by EFRE, INTERREG-V-Oberrhein, project 'InvaProtect', by the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) via the Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE) ('FlavePrevent'), and by EUPHRESKO ('Flavid').

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Kopacka I, Steffek R, Strauss G & Reisenzein H (2017) Modeling spatial and temporal spread of Flavescence dorée in two Austrian vine growing areas. IOBC-WPRS Bulletin 128, 66-74.

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SIMKEF – A DSS to predict *Drosophila suzukii* population dynamics

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² Center for Agricultural Technology Augustenberg (LTZ), Neßlerstraße 25, 76227 Karlsruhe, Germany

ABSTRACT

The spotted wing drosophila *Drosophila suzukii* is an invasive polyphagous pest of soft-skinned fruits which has caused widespread economic damage in orchards and vineyards in Germany since 2014. The pest's infestation intensity was highly dependent on the weather in Germany in the last years which prompted us to model the pest's life cycle rates dependent on air temperature and the relative air humidity (RH).

As minimum, optimum and maximum temperature we estimated 13.2, 26.7, 33.6 °C for oviposition, 13.2, 22.8, 29.7 °C for egg-to-adult development success, and 13.2, 26.5, 33.7 °C for the egg-to-adult development duration. The oviposition rate increased significantly with increasing RH but the correlation was rather poor. Furthermore, we found fruit temperature to be significantly higher in sunny and shady conditions than the air temperature measured by the nearest weather station. This might result in reduced survival rates, especially in the egg and larva life stage which showed 50% estimated survival at about 64 and 88 °h, respectively. Therefore, we generated functions describing fruit temperature which seems to be more appropriate for immature survival than the air temperature. Winter morph adults were significantly more cold tolerant than summer morphs and are assumed to be basically able to hibernate in Germany. In general, analyses suggest that the temperature is the main driver of *D. suzukii* population dynamics and the pest is only partially tolerant to extreme temperatures.

The modelled life cycle rates of *D. suzukii* are used in combination with phenological host plant models and weather data to predict infestation risk within the decision support system 'SIMKEF' for informed control measures, available at www.isip.de.

Which changes we have to expect in the dynamic of *Lobesia botrana* for Germany until 2060 AD?

Kartschall T., Schmidt K., Wodinski M., Menz C.

Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research and nemaplot GmbH Bonn[†]

ABSTRACT

The manifested climate change already is and will be in future a challenge for viticulture. The ongoing changes in phenology of *Vitis vinifera* (Vv) and in the dynamics of pest and diseases became widely recognized. We report on our methodology, model realizations and simulation results focused on climate impacts on the phenology of Vv and generation dynamic of *Lobesia botrana* (Lb).

The integrative model PhenologyVvMoth describes (like the name suggests) the phenology of Vv1,2,3) and the generation sequence, development stages and population dynamics of grape moth (both, Lb and *Eupoecilia ambiguella*4)) based on a Leslie scheme. Both model parts have been developed independently for research purposes on single sites of viticultural interest. Both are running inside a wrapper, which enables the common use of all daily weather, and they use the wrapper for the flexible configurable output of the simulated results, but they do not exchange simulated model variables.

Since the models are process-oriented, they make relatively extensive use of computational power. Regional applications were not the original aim of the initial model development, because they would be too time consuming on standard Windows computers. Therefore, we ported the source code (Fortran 2008) onto the High Performance Cluster at PIK (SUSE Linux) and parallelized the main time consuming instructions using the Intel® Fortran Compiler 19.0 family, which enabled a full source code compatibility of the Windows (x64) and the Linux versions.

In an impact study covering all Germany we used gridded retrospective (1901 AD to 2010 AD) and scenario (RCP 8.5) meteorological data (2010 AD to 2100 AD), interpolated from 1,038 stations onto 16,672 grid points.

Even both models did not interact, the results show a clearly visible synchronization in the timing of bud break and the emergence of the first adult Lb generation. Already during the last decades an average of about 3 to 4 days earlier emergence for the first generation of the adults of Lb became visible. This trend is likely to continue along the RCP 8.5 scenario in the coming decades. For example, the simulation results for the period from 2031 to 2060 indicate that the first generation adults will occur about 10 days earlier, which would be at least a doubling of the acceleration. The already predicted synchronization with the bud break of varieties of Vv

cultivated in Germany will largely be maintained with a slight further advance of the moth activities of 1 to 2 days.

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Predicting field population dynamics of anholocyclic hibernating grape phylloxera (*Daktulosphaira vitifoliae* Fitch) in commercial vineyards under climate change conditions: Pilot study year 2019: Validating a collecting strategy for individual fields.

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ABSTRACT

Temperature changes and phenological mismatches due to climate change may have important consequences on the population dynamics of root-feeding herbivores. Grape phylloxera hibernates on root galls as asexual first stages instar and moves upwards towards the leaves as the vegetation progresses. Knowledge of the temporal and spatial dynamics of this migration of motile instars is sparse and no studies have been performed in commercial vineyards neither grafted nor own-rooted. Observations on yellow sticky traps in vineyards were done to elucidate the wind drift of motile first instar phylloxera (crawler) towards commercial vineyards, which were found mainly in late summer. In recent years anholocyclic grape phylloxera populations are reported that overwinter on roots and move upwards to infest leaves of commercial vineyards (either *V. vinifera* or interspecific hybrids) in spring. These hosts were rarely infested in the decades before. Thus a leaf-feeding population is being established with changed feeding performance (named biotype G) with serious impact to the vines. In order to develop a strategy to combat the first generation leaf-feeding crawlers in commercial vineyards a precise timing to employ plant protection is required. Thus, accurate prediction modules for grape phylloxera occurring as latent vineyard populations are needed.

Here we present an overview of our project to develop prediction modules for IPM of grape phylloxera. The first years results of a pilot study to validate adequate sampling techniques and evaluation parameters are presented as a basis to develop a representative data collection on phylloxera dynamics including different climates, soils and water regimes. Within one plot (academic vineyard in Tulln, AT) soil traps were installed and sampled three times a week to monitor the upward insect movement. Plasting rings were used to monitor insects moving upwards via the stem and yellow sticky traps were installed 2.50 m above the canopy to monitor winged (sexual) and wind-drifted asexual instars (once a week). Our results show first catches in

April in the soil traps, with new generations migrating in ca. 25 d intervals. As expected the root migrating numbers of instars caught progressed towards the season. The first catches at the plasting ring were found in Juli, but massively increasing in August and September, confirming the observation of root to leaf-feeding switches in commercial vineyards. The catches in sticky traps increased according to the stem traps. We found very few winged instars (Sexuparae) in the sticky traps starting in September.

Our experience showed a major impact of the soil, spatial distance and numbers of traps. The monitoring in 3 d intervals seemed to adequate for data robustness and work efficiency. We suggest a minimum of five traps per vineyard “phylloxeration” zone (center vs. margin of the center) to be monitored in order to produce relevant data for modeling. In the next steps we enlarge the monitoring of latent grape phylloxera populations to further regions, climates and soils sites, employ a validation of different models to analyze the data in order to predict mobility of root-feeding hibernating phylloxera over the vegetation season.

Day 2

Tuesday, 18 February
8, rue Nic Kieffer L-5551
Institut Viti-vinicole (IVV), Remich

Epidemiological models for vineyard diseases. Why we should trust in them?

González-Domínguez¹ E., Legler¹ S., Caffi² T., Fedele² G., Rossi² V.

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ABSTRACT

Directive 128/2009/EC on the Sustainable Use of Pesticides makes mandatory the adoption of integrated pest management (IPM) across Europe. In IPM, farming systems should be less intensive with reduced inputs of pesticides. To achieve this goal, the directive promotes the implementation of tools for pest monitoring and decision making, and models are key components of any decision-support tool for plant disease control. Plant disease models are simplifications of the relationships between pathogens, crops, the environment and crop management actions that cause epidemic development over time and/or space. Plant disease models have been developed in the last decades for the most important diseases affecting grapevine leaves and bunches. However, the adoption by farmers as part of their IPMs strategies is still low. Several reasons can be related with this constraint, but a crucial aspect is the quality of the models in terms of accuracy, robustness and usefulness.

Here we present the structure and main characteristics of the models developed at the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Piacenza, Italy) by using a mechanistic approach. Mechanistic modelling uses fundamental knowledge of divide the pathogen life cycle into different state variables, and changes from one state to the following state were determined by rate variables that depend on external conditions like weather variables, plant susceptibility or crop management actions. In the following step, models are validated in multiple epidemiological conditions (usually, in several years and locations) to verify whether they are able to correctly predict the disease. Finally, models are evaluated within IPM programs to verify whether they are useful for improving disease control tactics. This procedure is complex and the implementation is expensive and time-consuming, but it guarantees more reliable, robust and flexible models

compared to different modelling approaches. Models have been developed for downy and powdery mildews, black rot, botrytis bunch rot, Phomopsis cane and leaf spot, and other diseases, which are currently implemented in a DSS called vite.net and broadly used by farmers in Italy, Spain, Portugal, Romania, Greece, and other countries.

The viticultural decision support platforms Agrometeo and VitiMeteo

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ABSTRACT

The negative effects of plant protection products on the human health and the environment have become a major concern for consumers and politics in Europe. In the last years new policies for risk mitigation and reduction of use of synthetic pesticides has been enforce in Germany and Switzerland. National Action Plans (NAP) to reduce the risks and the use of plant protection products have been developed. Viticulture is an important consumer of plant protection products especially fungicides. In order to achieve the objectives of the NAP a possible strategy is to spray according to the epidemic of diseases and pests by following decision support systems (DSS). The platform VitiMeteo offers a wide set of forecasting models for viticulture including downy and powdery mildew, black rot, grape berry moth and rust mite. There are also monitoring tools for diseases and pests as well as further practical information on plant protection issues. VitiMeteo was developed jointly by two research institutes the Staatliches Weinbauinstitut Freiburg (WBI, Germany) and Agroscope (Switzerland). A consortium was built with the company Geosens (Germany) in order to develop the forecasting softwares and decision support systems. Each institute is running his own internet website with specific tools and feature for each country but the core of the system is the same and was developed conjointly. A validation of the VitiMeteo-Oidium model over six years in different Swiss vineyards showed an average reduction of one spray per year with no reduction in efficacy. The VitiMeteo-Plasmopara model enable to spray according to the epidemics of downy mildew and allow a better control of the disease. However, the reduction of the number of sprays strongly depends on the weather conditions of the year. For Switzerland a further significant tool is crop adapted spraying, a method which adapts the applied quantity of plant protection products to the leaf surface. All these forecasting systems and tools are freely available for the winegrowers on the platform www.vitimeteo.de and www.agrometeo.ch. The use of these platforms will help the winegrowers to meet the current society expectations.

Downy mildew forecast model and its successful application in practise (Rheingau, Germany)

Berkelmann-Löhnertz B., Ehlig A., Baus O.

Hochschule Geisenheim University, Department of Crop Protection

ABSTRACT

Forecast models are an important component of integrated pest management that help to reduce pesticide use. With the utilization of these models, control of *Plasmopara viticola*, one of the most destructive fungi in viticulture, can be optimized with a long-term goal of saving fungicide treatments in accordance to the severity of the epidemic course.

In the Rheingau region, the optimized Geisenheim *Plasmopara* forecast model has been successfully used in viticulture consultancy for almost fifteen years. The newly developed primary infection model has helped us predicting the likelihood of soil-borne infections using agrometeorological parameters and biological processes such as maturation and germination of oospores in upper soil layers with the aid of a microclimate model adapted from arable crops, splash droplets height as a function of precipitation and leaf wetness, respectively. The aforementioned data were incorporated in sub-models.

In addition, a "primary infection index" was created based on the new microclimate model, since the likelihood of soil borne infection is greatest when there are small puddles on the ground from which the newly released zoospores can be taken up by splash.

The new *Plasmopara* soil-borne infection model represents an important supplement to the existing model predicting secondary (leaf-borne) infections. On this basis, both "false positive" and "false negative" forecasts were considerably reduced. Therefore, one of the outstanding features of the new model is the high forecasting precision. With this knowledge, fungicide sprayings can be applied according to the actual infection level. In addition, the potential of *Plasmopara* fungicides with different modes of action and, therefore, application time (protective, curative) is better exploited. Especially in "difficult *Plasmopara* years" with strong precipitation in spring and frequent severe rainfall provoking splash events, grape growers of the Rheingau region benefit from the excellent forecast quality of the Geisenheim *Plasmopara* forecast model. In the near future, the integration of a CO₂ module aimed at policy counselling regarding climate impacts is planned. In addition, the Geisenheim *Plasmopara* forecast model is to be adapted to new fungus-tolerant grape varieties and to organic viticulture in order to reduce fungicide (copper) applications even more.

Application of the decision support tools of the VitiMeteo platform in practical viticulture

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ABSTRACT

The overarching aim of the National Action Plan on Sustainable Use of Plant Protection Products in Germany (NAP Germany) is to limit the amount of pesticides used to the minimum. Forecasting models, expert systems, and decision support tools play a key role in this process. VitiMeteo (VM) is an intensively used internet platform which provides forecasting models as well as weather- and monitoring data for viticulture in the South-West of Germany (Baden-Württemberg). VM was established in 2002 and is a cooperative project between the State Institute of Viticulture and Enology (Freiburg, Germany), Agroscope (Switzerland) and the company GEOsens (Schallstadt; Germany), and is further supported by other research institutes. Besides Baden-Württemberg and Switzerland, VM models are widely applied in other countries in Europe. Currently, simulation models for the economically most relevant grapevine diseases and pests are integrated. The models are complemented by a monitoring system which helps to apply sustainable control strategies in practice. VM allows the development of modern, flexible tools for research and provides free of charge, up-to-date, online information on disease risks and weather data for viticultural practice. The results are available for consultants and winegrowers in Baden-Württemberg via the website www.vitimeteo.de.

The successful application of the internet platform www.vitimeteo.de and the VM models in practical viticulture is based on the following key elements:

- Annual meetings for validation and evaluation of models and model based strategies
- Constant development of model-based plant protection strategies for winegrowers:
 - Example 1: Downy mildew - During the past decades the State Institute for Viticulture and Enology has developed and established an effective strategy to control grapevine downy mildew based on the model “VitiMeteo Downy Mildew”.
 - Example 2: Powdery mildew - “VitiMeteo Powdery Mildew” provides decision support for the optimum period between two spray applications. The State Institute for Viticulture, Oenology and Fruit Technology (Weinsberg, Germany) has developed a strategy based on this model, which has been tested successfully in numerous long-term field trials at the partner institutes as well as other locations.
- Continuous knowledge transfer through seminars, workshops, trainings, publications etc.
- Because the research institutions own the software, new results and improvements are quickly integrated.

- Important model parameters may be varied in all expert softwares. This parameterization enables "what-if"-scenarios and is essential for the optimization of models.

"VitiMeteo" is a prime example of a positive collaborative long-term project between scientists, consultants and winegrowers. It is currently undergoing mayor developments in order to implement novel applications and to provide a variable, interactive and user-friendly system for sustainable plant protection.

From Modelling to Decision Support and Back – Lessons Learend in 20 Years

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ABSTRACT

Operating a decision support system (DSS) for a big area is a task quite different from developing a model for a specific disease. Yet some of the practical challenges have direct impact on the model development. Model development and calibration are usually performed with the hardware or – in a broader sense – the data sources available at the time. These data sources change in multiple ways over time. Weather stations will remain a key element, but there are other types of data sources available today like micro sensors or calculated data from meteorological models, networks or weather services. We need to develop a broader concept to understand in what ways different data sources impact our model's results. Such a concept is urgently needed in the wake of Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence. We will propose an outline and show how it can help to design models that are less dependent on the characteristics of particular data sources and helps us determine the minimum requirements for a given model.

Zusammenfassung

Der Betrieb eines Decision Support Systems (DSS) für eine große Region ist eine andere Aufgabe als die Entwicklung eines Modells für eine bestimmte Krankheit. Einige der praktischen Anforderungen haben jedoch direkte Auswirkungen auf die Modellentwicklung. Die Modellentwicklung und -kalibrierung erfolgt in der Regel mit der zur Zeit verfügbaren Hardware oder - im weiteren Sinne - den verfügbaren Datenquellen. Diese Datenquellen ändern sich im Laufe der Zeit auf vielfältige Weise. Wetterstationen werden ein wichtiges Element bleiben, aber es gibt heute andere Arten von Datenquellen wie Mikrosensoren oder berechnete Daten aus meteorologischen Modellen, Netzwerken oder Wetterdiensten. Wir müssen ein umfassenderes Konzept entwickeln um zu verstehen wie sich verschiedene Datenquellen auf die Ergebnisse unseres Modells auswirken. Ein solches Konzept ist im Zuge von Machine Learning und künstlicher Intelligenz dringend erforderlich. Wir werden einen Entwurf hierfür vorstellen und zeigen wie er dazu beitragen kann Modelle so zu gestalten, dass sie weniger abhängig von den Merkmalen bestimmter Datenquellen sind, und uns helfen, die Mindestanforderungen für ein Modell zu bestimmen.

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